

Multi-scale Multi-block covariance descriptor with feature selection

Abdelmalik Moujahid and Fadi Dornaika

Published in: Neural Computing and Applications, Springer-Verlag, 2020. DOI: 10.1007/s00521-019-04135-7. Published online 15 March 2019.

Abstract This paper investigates a compact face texture representation able to cover the most discriminant features of facial images. The compactness is achieved by the proposed Pyramid Multi-Level (PML) covariance texture descriptor and the feature selection process that is applied on the raw extracted features. In fact, we introduce a framework based mainly on two new aspects. Firstly, we consider an extension of the original covariance descriptor that relies on de-noised covariance matrices obtained using texture descriptors such as local binary pattern and quaternionic local ranking binary pattern images. Secondly, we exploit the resulting covariance descriptor using a PML face representation which allows a multi-level multi-scale feature extraction. Experiments conducted on four public face datasets show the efficacy of the proposed face descriptor and the associated selection schemes.

Keywords Face texture representation; Feature selection; Face Recognition

1 Introduction

Extracting descriptors from raw images have received a lot of attention during the last three decades. This is due to the fact the applications that are based on images expand rapidly. These applications can be 3D modeling of scenes, object categorization [5], Content-based image retrieval systems [9], face image analysis [2, 4, 53], image-based localization [8, 6], to mention a few. For tasks that require semantic interpretation (e.g., object recognition), it has been argued that the performance of learning systems depends heavily on the quality and type of the image descriptor. But also, it has been shown that division-based strategies for image representation are very useful to enhance the quality of the extracted features.

A. Moujahid
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain
E-mail: abdelmalik.moujahid@ehu.eus
F. Dornaika
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain

Multi-block (MB) face representation is a common method for capturing local features and is known to compensate for non-uniformities in illumination and reflectance. In fact, it has been shown that face recognition based on local binary pattern (LBP) histograms can be enhanced if one uses the histograms computed over several non-overlapping blocks of the face image [14,15,16]. This division-based strategy, known as MB-LBP, has been applied successfully in many domains like face recognition, image retrieval or texture analysis[17,18,19,20]. Multi-block (MB) face representation proceeds by dividing an input image into a grid of non-overlapping or overlapping regions (blocks) and then extracts a regional descriptor from each block. The final descriptor is then obtained by concatenating all regional descriptors.

However, in order to extract not only the local features but also to get some global context information, other division-based strategies have proven to be more effective and highly discriminative. Existing methods include multi-level (ML) representation used in the age estimation and gender classification topics ([21,22]), pyramid-based multi-scale (PMS) representation reported for face recognition [23], and finally pyramid multi-level (PML) representation proposed recently for facial demographic estimation [24].

ML representation is achieved by using different multi-block divisions of the same face image. Then, the texture descriptor is applied to each block. Finally, all extracted descriptors are concatenated into an enhanced feature descriptor which is used as the face descriptor. This face representation has been extended to a real pyramid representation adopting an explicit pyramid construction of the face image. This pyramid represents the image at different scales. For each scale or level, a corresponding MB representation is performed. At each level i , the associated image is divided into i^2 blocks. Thus, the total number of blocks is given by $B = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} i^2 = \ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)/6$. For each block a regional feature descriptor is extracted and finally the PML-based feature descriptor is obtained by concatenating all regional B descriptors.

All these division-based strategies for face representation have been mainly considered for descriptors based on one single type of features (e.g., LBP) [24, 41,37]. In this work, we introduce an effective approach for face representation that relies on the PML face representation that exploits second order statistics of several local texture features such as LBP, QLRBP, gradients, and different color spaces. Our main contribution is the introduction of the PML-based covariance descriptor and its use in the face analysis field. The proposed face descriptor has three interesting properties: (i) thanks to the PML representation, scales and face parts are explicitly encoded in the final descriptor without having to detect the facial points, (ii) the covariance descriptor (second order statistics) encodes spatial features of any type, and thus the final descriptor naturally fuses several state-of-the-art texture features, (iii) it is compact when it is compared to the classic concatenation of PML based descriptors.

As stated above, the PML descriptor is obtained by concatenating all individual descriptors corresponding to each block at each level of the pyramid. This may result in a large descriptor which may contain a lot of redundant and unreliable information, and therefore, feature selection algorithms are required to extract the most relevant and discriminative features of the PML-based descriptors. Two selection schemes are proposed. The first one aims at selecting the most relevant features (bins) in the final descriptor. The second one seeks the image regions or

blocks used to compute the descriptor, and we are mainly concerned in determining what regional descriptors are more relevant and should be considered in the classification phase. We apply the two proposed schemes on the PML representation of LBP, HOG, and covariance.

1.1 Motivation and paper contribution

The paper has the following contributions.

1. We propose the Pyramid Multi Level-Covariance descriptor and apply it to the problem of face image classification.
2. We apply attribute and block selection to the final PML descriptors.
3. We provide a performance evaluation of the above proposals on four benchmark face databases.

We target a face representation that can be compact and contains rich information about faces. The compactness is achieved by the adopted texture descriptor (the covariance descriptor) and the feature selection process that is applied on the raw extracted features. Our previous findings showed that the covariance descriptor can be used as a powerful discriminant texture descriptor [25,26].

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews some backgrounds and reviews some texture descriptors. Section 4 describes our proposed face descriptor and the selection scheme. This section presents the covariance descriptor and the Pyramid-Multi Level face representation. Experimental results and global comparison are reported in Section 4 and 5 respectively. We conclude this work in Section 6.

2 Background

This section presents some backgrounds on feature selection and face image descriptors.

2.1 Feature selection

The main objective of feature selection is to determine the best subsets of features (or variables) for performing statistical analysis task or building a machine learning model [27,28]. In the context of supervised learning, feature selection methods can be categorized into two classes: filter-based and wrapper-based methods. Wrapper-based feature selection requires the definition of both a predictive model and a search algorithm to score feature subsets. The optimal subset is obtained by training and testing a specific classification model while maximizing the classification performance. This renders this approach more dependent on the specific classification algorithm.

Alternatively, filter-based feature selection assess the relevance of features by considering only the intrinsic characteristics of the data. In this case, a suitable ranking criterion is used to score the variables and low-scoring features are ignored

in the classification phase. These techniques have proven to be more suited to deal with very high-dimensional datasets and are computationally efficient.

In the past decade, a number of performance criteria have been proposed for filter-based feature selection, such as mutual information [60], Relief [61], Laplacian score [62] and Fisher score [59]. A survey on feature selection can be found in [12, 13].

2.2 Face descriptors

In the past decades, texture analysis has been extensively studied. A wide variety of texture feature extraction methods have been proposed. Among the proposed approaches Local Binary Pattern (LBP) [19] has been known as one of the most successful statistical approach due to its efficacy, robustness against illumination changes and relative fast calculation. Texture analysis and image feature extraction have been effectively used in face images. Since then several texture descriptors have been proposed (e.g., [34, 35, 36]). Many of them were also applied to face representation such as Binarized Statistical Image Features (BSIF) [37] and local ternary patterns [38].

In this section, we briefly present LBP, QLRBP, and HOG descriptors. In the next section, we present our proposed face descriptor as well as the scheme for kinship verification based on that descriptor.

2.2.1 Local Binary Patterns (LBP) descriptor

The original LBP operator replaces the value of the pixels of an image with decimal numbers, which are called LBPs or LBP codes that encode the local structure around each pixel [39]. Each central pixel is compared with its eight neighbors; the neighbors having smaller value than that of the central pixel will have the bit 0, and the other neighbors having value equal to or greater than that of the central pixel will have the bit 1. For each given central pixel, one can generate a binary number that is obtained by concatenating all these binary bits in a clockwise direction, which starts from the one of its top-left neighbor. The resulting decimal value of the generated binary number replaces the central pixel value. The histogram of LBP labels (the frequency of occurrence of each code) calculated over a region or an image can be used as a texture descriptor of that image.

2.2.2 Quaternionic Local Ranking Binary Pattern (QLRBP)

Several extensions of LBP to color have been proposed. The most well-known is the Opponent Color LBP. It describes color and texture jointly [11]. In recent times, the work described in [41] proposed the Quaternionic Local Ranking Binary Pattern to represent color images by quaternion notations (i.e., pure imaginary quaternions). Then, they use a reference quaternion (reference color) in order to retrieve a similarity score between the current pixel color and the reference color. These similarities define a phase map on which classic LBP operator can be applied. For each reference color, there will be one phase map.

In our work, we are interested in the phase maps in order to use them as feature maps.

2.2.3 HOG descriptor

Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)[42] is a feature descriptor used to detect objects in computer vision and image processing. The HOG descriptor technique counts occurrences of gradient orientation in localized portions of an image - cells and blocks.

3 Proposed scheme

This section presents our proposed scheme for face image representation. The scheme has three main components: (i) the covariance descriptor of face texture, (ii) the Pyramid-multi-level face representation, and (iii) attribute or block selection.

3.1 Covariance descriptor

The original covariance descriptor is a statistic based feature proposed for generic object detection and texture classification tasks [43]. Instead of using histograms, the work of [43] computes the covariance matrices among the color channels and gradient images. Compared with other descriptors, the covariance descriptor lies in a very low-dimensional space, and gives a natural way of fusing multiple types of features as long as they can be presented spatially. Thus, this descriptor can benefit from any progress made in image feature extraction. In addition, this descriptor lends itself nicely to efficient implementation whenever the image regions are rectangular by exploiting the integral image concept as it is described in [43].

Since its introduction the covariance descriptor has not received much attention by researchers despite its ability to incorporate a large number of existing and recent texture features. This motivates us to propose an extension of this descriptor that includes two new aspects. First, we compute the covariance matrices using texture descriptors such as LBP and QLRBP images. Second, we exploit this covariance descriptor using a Pyramid-Multi Level (PML) face representation which allows a multi-level multi scale feature extraction. The PML representation will be described in the next section.

Fig. 1 A schematic representation of the covariance descriptor. The input face image is represented by a set of d texture and color features that will be fused in the final covariance descriptor.

Given a color image, we start by extracting the local features that are represented in 2D maps having the same spatial grid as the original image. More precisely, we extract 20 different channels: (i) 6 channels corresponding to the color components in both RGB and HSV spaces; (ii) 8 channels for x and y coordinates and the first and second derivative of the image intensity with respect to x and y ; (iii) 3 channels corresponding to three Local Binary Pattern images [19, 18, 39] obtained by combining three different modes for 8 neighboring points at radius equal to 1; (iv) and finally 3 channels for the three phase images associated to the QLRBP descriptor [41].

This descriptor is computed as follows: let I denote a $M \times N$ intensity image, and V be the set of the $M \times N \times d$ dimensional feature images extracted from I (see Figure 1 for a graphical illustration). Thus, V can be seen as a set of d 2D arrays (channels) where every array corresponds to a given image feature such as horizontal coordinate, vertical coordinate, color, image derivatives, and filter responses, etc. This multi-dimensional array can be written as $V(x; y) = \phi(I; x; y)$ where ϕ is a function that extracts image features.

For a given image region $\mathcal{R} \in I$ containing n pixels, let $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}_{i=1\dots n}$ denote the d -dimensional feature vectors obtained by ϕ within \mathcal{R} . According to [43], the region \mathcal{R} can be described by a $d \times d$ covariance matrix:

$$\Sigma_{\mathcal{R}} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{v}_i - \bar{\mathbf{v}})(\mathbf{v}_i - \bar{\mathbf{v}})^T, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{v}}$ is the mean vector of $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}_{i=1\dots n}$. The sample covariance matrix, $\Sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$, represents the second order statistics of the d dimensional vectors $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}$ within the region \mathcal{R} .

As stated above, the sample covariance matrix is obtained using different channels of different nature. This, may introduce some randomness effects which may result in a biased estimator of the natural estimator for the population covariance $\Sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$. In order to attenuate these randomness effects we have adopted the theory of random matrices of high dimension to de-noise the sample matrix $\Sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$ [56]. The de-noised sample covariance is then used as an estimator for $\Sigma_{\mathcal{R}}$.

Let $D = \text{diag}(\Sigma_{\mathcal{R}})$ and $C = D^{-1/2} \Sigma_{\mathcal{R}} D^{-1/2}$, so that C is the sample correlation matrix. The presence in C of eigenvalues exceeding some limit value λ_{max} is synonym of the presence of signal rather than pure noise (See [57, 58]). Therefore, a cleaned correlation matrix \bar{C} can be constructed by considering only those eigenvectors whose eigenvalues are greater than λ_{max} . Suppose there are k eigenvalues larger than λ_{max} , then according to [58], a cleaned correlation matrix \bar{C} can be constructed as follows:

$$\bar{C} = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i \nu_i \nu_i^T + a I_d \quad (2)$$

where I_d is $d \times d$ identity matrix, and a is a constant such that $\text{tr}(\bar{C}) = \text{tr}(C) = d$. Thus, we have:

$$a = \frac{\lambda_{k+1} + \dots + \lambda_d}{d} \quad (3)$$

Then, the cleaned sample covariance matrix is constructed as

$$\bar{\Sigma}_{\mathcal{R}} = D^{1/2} \bar{C} D^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Under the Log-Euclidean Riemannian metric, it is possible to measure the distance between covariance matrices. Given two covariance matrices Σ_1 and Σ_2 , their distance is given by,

$$d(\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2) = \|\log(\Sigma_1) - \log(\Sigma_2)\|_{\ell_2}, \quad (5)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{\ell_2}$ is the ℓ_2 vector norm and $\log(\Sigma)$ is the matrix logarithm of the square matrix Σ .

Thus, every image region, \mathcal{R} , can be characterized by the vectorized form of the matrix $\log(\bar{\Sigma}_{\mathcal{R}})$. Since this is a symmetric matrix, then the feature vector can be described by a $d \times (d + 1)/2$ where d is the number of channels. Thus, the covariance descriptor of an image region is given by the following vector:

$$\text{COV}(\mathcal{R}) = \log(\bar{\Sigma}_{\mathcal{R}}) \quad (6)$$

Since the number of channels used is 20, it follows that the covariance descriptor of each region is described by $20 * 21 / 2 = 210$ features. Figure 1 illustrates a schematic representation of the covariance descriptor applied to an input face image.

3.2 Pyramid Multi-Level (PML) face representation

The PML representation adopts an explicit pyramid representation of the original image. This pyramid represents the image at different scales. For each scale or level, a corresponding Multi-block representation is performed. Each image of the pyramid will be divided into an appropriate number of square blocks. The descriptor of each resulting block is then extracted using the steps described in the previous section. Figure 2 (Bottom) illustrates the PML principle for a pyramid of three levels associated with a face image.

Given the number of levels, ℓ , and the size of an individual square block ($b \times b$), the size of the resulting square image at level i is given by $i \times (b, b)$. The total number of blocks is given by $B = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} i^2 = \ell(\ell + 1)(2\ell + 1)/6$. All blocks have a size of $b \times b$ pixels. At level 1 (the top of the pyramid), the whole image is reduced to one single block of $b \times b$ pixels.

Formally, the PML representation of an image is obtained as follows: Let f be an image of size $N \times N$. Let P be its pyramid representation with ℓ levels, $P = \{L_1, \dots, L_{\ell}\}$ [55]. The size of the images L_i should meet the following. Each level L_i is represented by a partition of square blocks of size $\frac{N}{\ell} \times \frac{N}{\ell}$, $L_i = \{B_{i,1}, \dots, B_{i,n_i}\}$, where $n_i = i^2$. Given a value ℓ , we pose $b = \frac{N}{\ell}$. Thus, the size of square blocks at all levels is $b \times b$. We point out that P_{ℓ} is f and $P_1 = B_{1,1}$ (coarsest resolution).

The pyramid representation of an image f by ℓ levels is the sequence L_1, \dots, L_{ℓ} such that:

$$L_i = \{B_{i,1}, \dots, B_{i,n_i}\} \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, \ell \quad \text{and } n_i = i^2 \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2 (Top) Multi-block covariance descriptor. For a given image divided into different blocks, the covariance descriptor is computed for each block using d different features which gives rise to a descriptor of size $d(d+1)/2$. The multi-block covariance descriptor is then obtained by concatenating all the individual descriptors. **(Bottom) Pyramid Multi-Level (PML) covariance descriptor** for a pyramid of three levels. At each level i the image is divided into i^2 blocks resulting to a total number of blocks given by $B = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} i^2 = \ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)/6$. For each block a regional multi-block covariance descriptor (\mathbf{f}_i) is extracted and finally the PML-based feature descriptor is obtained by concatenating all regional descriptors ($\mathbf{f} = \{\mathbf{f}_1, \mathbf{f}_2, \dots, \mathbf{f}_B\}$).

3.3 PML covariance descriptor

Once the PML representation is obtained, the local features of each block at each level are described by the covariance descriptor as shown at the top part of Figure 2. Concretely, the PML Descriptor at the level i ($i = 1, \dots, \ell$) is given by:

$$\text{COV}(L_i) = \text{COV}(B_{i,1}) \parallel \dots \parallel \text{COV}(B_{i,n_i})$$

where \parallel denotes the concatenation operator. Therefore, we define the PML Descriptor using ℓ levels of the pyramid representation as follows:

$$\ell\text{-PMLD}(f) = \text{COV}(L_1) \parallel \dots \parallel \text{COV}(L_\ell) \quad (8)$$

We can observe that the total number of blocks in a pyramid of depth ℓ is $\sum_{i=1}^{\ell} i^2 = \frac{\ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)}{6}$. Hence, ℓ -PMLD is composed of $\frac{d(d+1)}{2} \cdot \frac{\ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)}{6}$ elements, since the number of elements of COV descriptor is $\frac{d(d+1)}{2}$.

3.4 Feature selection

As stated above, the PML descriptor is obtained by concatenating all individual descriptors corresponding to each block at each level of the pyramid. The final descriptor is associated to all resolution and to all image parts. This may result in a large descriptor which may contain a lot of redundant and unreliable information. In data mining, it is well known that feature selection can avoid, on one hand, over-fitting problems while improving classification model performance, and on the other hand, to provide efficient and more cost-effective learning models [54].

In this work, we use Fisher scoring of the features in order to extract the most relevant and discriminative features of the PML-based descriptors. Fisher scoring is a supervised feature selection method which uses class labels to identify features with best discriminant ability [59]. The data space spanned by the selected features is such that the distances between data points in different classes are as large as possible, while the distances between data points in the same class are as small as possible.

Fig. 3 Illustration of Fisher score for a data set of 2D samples (two features) belonging to four classes.

Let $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ denote the PML descriptor associated with a given face images. The Fisher score of the r th feature is given by:

$$S_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^c n_i (\mu_r^i - \mu_r)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^c n_i (\sigma_r^i)^2}, \quad (9)$$

Algorithm 1 PML covariance descriptor (PML-COV)

Input:

- A face image
- PML parameters: ℓ (the pyramid level); b (the individual block size)

Output: PML-COV descriptor;**For the input face image:**

- 1: Compute the PML representation using Eq. (7);
 - 2: Compute the individual covariance descriptor for each block in the PML representation using Eqs. (1), (2), (3), (4), and (6);
 - 3: Concatenate the individual descriptors using Eq. (8);
-

where n_i is the size of i th class, and μ_r^i and σ_r^i refer to the mean and variance of the r th feature of the i th class, respectively. μ_r refers to the global mean of the r th feature. In the above formula, the numerator quantifies the class separability (it should be high for relevant features) while the denominator (it should be very small for relevant features) quantifies the class compactness. The intuition behind Fisher score is given by Figure 3. This figure illustrates a set of samples belonging to four classes that live in a 2D dimensional space. It is obvious that the score of the first feature is much higher than that of the second feature meaning that the first feature is more relevant than the first one.

The output of the feature selection is a vector of real scores allowing the ranking of the attributes composing the PML covariance descriptor. From this obtained ordering, several feature subsets can be chosen by setting a cutoff for the selected features. In this work, we have adopted the threshold-based criterion. In fact, we have analyzed different cutoff values ranging from 10 to 80% of the relevant features. Once the selection is fixed, it is applied to both the training and test sets.

For block based selection, for which a feature is a sub-vector, a similar formula is used where we use the mean vectors instead of scalar means and the class variances are replaced by the sum of variances of the sub-vector elements.

4 Experimental results

4.1 Face databases

The proposed scheme has been evaluated on four widely used public face databases: Georgia Tech [46], Yale [44], ORL [45], and FEI face databases [47]. A summary of relevant details of these databases is reported in Table 1. The Georgia Tech face database contains images of 50 people taken in two or three sessions between June and November 1999 at the Center for Signal and Image Processing at Georgia Institute of Technology. All people in the database are represented by 15 color JPEG images with cluttered background taken at resolution 640×480 pixels. The images correspond to frontal and/or tilted faces with different facial expressions, lighting conditions and scale. The size of the faces in these images has been fixed to 140×140 pixels.

The Yale dataset was constructed at the Yale Center for the Computational Vision and Control. It contains 165 grayscale images of 15 subjects (11 images per

subject), under various facial expressions or configurations. The Yale face database is characterized by different configurations, specifically: center-light, with glasses, happy, left-light, without glasses, normal, right-light, sad, sleepy, surprised and winking. In addition, the faces are not centered. For this database, we have adopted face images with size 240x240 pixels, with 256 gray levels per pixel.

The ORL database contains a set of face images taken at Cambridge University. The database was used in the context of a face recognition project carried out in collaboration with the Speech, Vision and Robotics Group of the Cambridge University Engineering Department [45]. The database contains 400 Grey images corresponding to ten different images of 40 distinct subjects. For some subjects, the images were taken at different times, varying the lighting, facial expressions (open/closed eyes, smiling/not smiling) and facial details (glasses/no glasses). In this case, we have resized the face images to 90x90 pixels, with 256 gray levels per pixel.

The FEI face database is a Brazilian face database that contains a set of face images taken between June 2005 and March 2006 at the Artificial Intelligence Laboratory of FEI in São Bernardo do Campo, Sao Paulo, Brazil. There are 14 images for each of 200 individuals, a total of 2800 images. All images are colorful and taken against a white homogeneous background in an upright frontal position with profile rotation of up to about 180 degrees. Scale might vary about 10% and the original size of each image is 640x480 pixels.

Figure 4 illustrates some samples from the above face datasets.

Fig. 4 A sample of faces images from Georgia (A), ORL (B), Yale (C) and FEI (D) Face Databases.

4.2 Experimental setup

For each database, the face images are first converted to face image descriptors. The obtained dataset is split into five folds having equal sizes. That is to say, our evaluation adopts five fold cross-validation. For the training part, we perform both attributes and blocks selection using the different feature selection algorithms

Table 1 Description of the Face databases used in this work.

Dataset	Subjects	Images per subject	Size (pixels)
Georgia	50	15	140×140
Yale	15	11	240×240
ORL	40	10	90×90
FEI	50	14	640×480

Table 2 A summary of the different PML-based features descriptors and their dimensions.

Level	Blocks	PML-LBP	PML-HOG	PML-COV
4	30	1770	6240	6300
5	55	3245	11440	11550
6	91	5369	18928	19110

Table 3 Feature selection based on individual attributes: Classification accuracy (percent) of different PML-based hand-crafted descriptors on different face databases as a function of the percentage of **selected attributes**. Results correspond to a pyramid of 6 levels. Feature selection has been performed using Fisher score algorithm. Best results are displayed in bold.**PML-LBP**

% of selected attributes	ORL	Georgia	Yale	FEI
100%	99.00	85.2	78.08	92.21
80%	99.00	86.13	78.76	92.87
60%	98.75	85.07	80.81	93.35
40%	98.50	83.87	81.77	94.00
20%	98.25	80.67	83.94	92.87

PML-HOG

% of selected attributes	ORL	Georgia	Yale	FEI
100%	96.25	78.93	86.26	95.31
80%	96.75	80.27	88.71	95.52
60%	96.50	79.60	88.71	95.44
40%	96.25	81.20	86.67	95.70
20%	96.50	79.07	84.62	94.44

PML-COV

% of selected attributes	ORL	Georgia	Yale	FEI
100%	98.50	93.60	85.05	95.74
80%	98.50	94.00	83.69	95.95
60%	98.75	94.80	84.37	96.08
40%	98.50	94.80	85.05	96.00
20%	98.25	94.67	86.82	96.00

described previously. The output of each selection algorithm is a weight vector giving a ranking of attributes or blocks composing the descriptor. From this obtained ranking, several feature subsets can be chosen by setting a cutoff for the selected features (attributes or blocks). In this work, we have adopted threshold-based criterion. In fact, we have analyzed different cutoff values ranging from 20% to 90% of the relevant features (or blocks). Once the selection is fixed, it is applied on both the training and test sets. Finally, we evaluate the recognition rate on the test set

Table 4 Feature selection based on blocks: Classification accuracy (percent) of different PML-based hand-crafted descriptors on different face databases as a function of the percentage of **selected blocks**. Results correspond to a pyramid of 6 levels. Feature selection has been performed using Fisher score algorithm. Best results are displayed in bold.

PML-LBP				
% of selected blocks	ORL	Georgia	Yale	FEI
100%	99.00	85.2	78.08	92.21
80%	98.75	83.2	79.9	92.51
60%	98.25	82.67	79.49	92.64
40%	98.50	80.00	77.32	92.12
20%	97.00	75.47	72.15	89.38

PML-HOG				
% of selected blocks	ORL	Georgia	Yale	FEI
100%	96.25	78.93	86.26	95.31
80%	96.5	78.67	86.26	93.56
60%	97.50	79.47	85.86	93.25
40%	97.25	79.07	85.86	92.30
20%	97.00	76.93	83.41	91.94

PML-COV				
% of selected blocks	ORL	Georgia	Yale	FEI
100%	99.25	94.80	84.09	95.95
80%	99.25	94.93	84.77	95.82
60%	99.25	94.53	84.50	95.95
40%	99.50	94.67	82.45	95.95
20%	98.00	94.53	81.77	95.30

using the selected features or blocks. To this end, the test images are classified using the nearest neighbor classifier.

4.3 Performance evaluation

In this section, we study and compare the performance of the different PML face representations based on LBP, HOG, and COV descriptors. The performance has been evaluated as a function of the selected attributes and blocks. Table 2 illustrates a summary of the different PML-based descriptors and their dimensions. It is worthy mentioning that the dimension of these descriptors are not related to the original image size; rather they are depending on the number of pyramid levels and on the specific texture descriptor on which the PML is built.

As can be seen, by adopting six levels for the pyramid the dimensions of the PML-LBP descriptor, PML-HOG descriptor, and PML-COV descriptor are 5369, 18928, and 19110, respectively. Thus, the feature selection will help in order to reduce these dimensions, and thus making training and testing much more efficient.

In the following, two main configurations have been considered to implement the feature selection algorithms: (i) *Attribute selection*, which means that we compute the weight vectors in order to characterize the individual elements of a given descriptor, and (ii) *Block selection*, where the weight scores are assigned to blocks instead of individual attributes.

4.3.1 Attribute selection

As reported previously, to select subsets of relevant attributes we have considered different cutoff values ranging from 20% to only 80% of the relevant attributes that are found at the training phase.

Table 3 summarizes the accuracies obtained by the Nearest Neighbor classifier, on the four face datasets, as a function of the number of relevant attributes selected. These results correspond to the three descriptors PML-LBP, PML-HOG, and PML-COV for a pyramid of 6 levels. Feature selection has been performed using Fisher score algorithm. Best results are displayed in bold. The evaluation protocol adopts five fold cross-validation.

For the cases without attribute selection (first rows in the Table), we can observe that the PML-COV outperformed the two other descriptors on the four face datasets. In some cases, the improvements was as big as 18.14 %. With attribute selection, in general, the out-performance of the PML-COV descriptor was maintained. We can also observe that the attribute selection not only reduces sizes of the descriptors but contributes to a slight improvement of the classification. For example, when the PML-COV descriptor is used with 20% of the selected features the performance is almost equal to that one obtained without selection.

4.3.2 Block selection

Similarly, we have implemented feature selection by blocks which allows to select the most relevant blocks of the texture descriptors that best discriminate the input face images. Table 4 summarizes the classification accuracies (percent) of different PML-based hand-crafted descriptors on the four face databases as a function of the percentage of the selected blocks. Results correspond to a pyramid of 6 levels. Feature selection has been performed using Fisher score algorithm. Best results are displayed in bold. As can be seen from Tables 3 and 4, for PML-LBP and PML-HOG descriptors, the classification performance obtained by the attribute selection is slightly better than the one obtained with the block selection. For PML-COV, the performance obtained by block selection is slightly better than the one obtained with the attribute selection.

For a better visualization of the relationship between the selected blocks and the local regions of the face image, we have represented the block weights for all levels of the pyramid. Figures 5 and 6 depict respectively the weights of the PML-COV and PML-HOG pyramid blocks for the used four datasets. Red colors indicate large weights and blue ones indicate small weights.

We emphasize that the scoring weights of the blocks are computed using all face images forming the training set. Thus, the relevant blocks in these figures are computed by taking into account all face images where different backgrounds and lighting conditions are present.

From Figures 5 and 6, we can observe the following. First, very often block relevance is consistent over the levels of the constructed pyramid. In other words, a relevant block at low resolution (level one or two) will be associated with a relevant sub-block (entirely or partially within the field of view) in the higher levels. Second, block relevance is depending on both the dataset and the type of texture descriptor. The dependency of block relevance on a given dataset is obvious since each dataset can depict several types of variations that relate to

illuminations and face poses. For instance, since the FEI dataset depicts rotated faces, it follows that physical relevant face features can be located at different blocks. By comparing the PML-COV descriptor and the PML-HOG (Figure 5 and 6), we can see that the relevant blocks can be found in all regions of the face images whereas for the PML-HOG (Figure 6), the relevant blocks contain specific structures in the face images. The intuitive explanation for this observation is that the covariance descriptor is mainly describing discriminant texture, and color of faces so these tend to have large regions in any face image. On the other hand, the HOG descriptor mainly focus on facial shapes (e.g., hair delineation, face contour, eyes contours, etc)

Fig. 5 Contour plots of the Fisher score weight matrices showing the relevant block and their locations over each levels of the PML-COV. Red color refers to high value and blue to low value. (a) Georgia database, (b) ORL database, (c) Yale database and (d) FEI database

5 Global comparison

In this section we compare the performance of our proposed scheme with some existing results achieved on the ORL and Georgia databases. We have considered the following methods: collaborative representation based classifier (CRC) [49], sparse representation based classifier (SRC) [3], improved versions of CRC and SRC proposed in [53], nearest neighbor classifier (NNC), fast iterative shrinkage-thresholding algorithm (FISTA) [50], fusion classification method (FCM) [52], and multi-Grained Cascade Forest (gcForest) [2]. Table 5 summarizes the obtained classification scores (in percent) accomplished using the above methods. The number

Fig. 6 Contour plots of the Fisher score weight matrices showing the relevant block and their locations over each levels of the PML-HOG. Red color refers to high value and blue to low value. (a) Georgia database, (b) ORL database, (c) Yale database and (d) FEI database

Table 5 Classification accuracy (percent) using different methods. The number of images per subject is 5 for the ORL dataset and 7 for the Georgia dataset.

Method	ORL	Georgia
CRC [49]	88.10	58.50
SRC [3]	88.00	59.00
Improved CRC [53]	91.50	67.00
Improved SRC [53]	91.50	66.50
1-NN [48]	83.00	48.25
FISTA [50]	88.50	64.25
FCM [52]	89.00	62.00
gcForest [2]	91.00	77.50
PML-LBP	96.75	78.32
PML-HOG	91.75	67.38
PML-COV	98.25	93.27

of images per subject was fixed to 5 for the ORL dataset and 7 for the Georgia dataset. In the experiments, the parameter α of the improved versions of CRC and SRC are the ones that provided the best classification rate. For these versions, the number of nearest neighbors of the test sample is set to two times of the number of original training samples per class. The experimental results in Table 5 demonstrate that the proposed scheme can greatly improve the classification accuracy.

6 Conclusions

This paper introduced a compact face texture representation that has proven to be able to capture rich and relevant information about faces. More precisely, we proposed to use the multi-scale multi-block representation based on a non-biased estimator of the covariance descriptor. The original image is transformed to an image pyramid having l levels. At each level, an appropriate number of blocks are generated. The individual descriptors of all blocks are computed and then concatenated to get the face descriptor. This descriptor has been computed for three types of texture features: LBP, HOG, and Covariance.

We achieve descriptor compactness using either attribute selection and block selection. Experiments conducted on four face datasets show that the proposed PML Covariance can have more discriminant information than the PML adopting the LBP and the HOG features. The application domain does not require a real-time performance. Therefore, optimizing the computational cost of the descriptor extraction was out of the scope of the work. Nevertheless, speeding up the extraction process is feasible by adapting parallel implementation or using some dedicated algorithms like the one described in [1].

Future work would apply these descriptors to other face-based analysis such as kinship verification and pain assessment.

7 Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

1. Z. Yang and D. Jia and S. Ioannidis and N. Mi and B. Sheng. Intermediate Data Caching Optimization for Multi-Stage and Parallel Big Data Frameworks *IEEE 11th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*, 2018.
2. Z. Zhou and J. Feng. Deep Forest: Towards an Alternative to Deep Neural Networks . *arXiv:1702.08835v2*, 2017.
3. A. Yang, S. Sastry, A. Ganesh, and Y. Ma. Fast ℓ_1 -minimization algorithms and an application in robust face recognition: a review. *IEEE International Conference on Image Processing*, 2010.
4. Z. Lou and F. Alnajjar and J. M. Alvarez and N. Hu and T. Gevers Expression-Invariant Age Estimation Using Structured Learning *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 40,2,365-375,2018.
5. A. Krizhevsky and I. Sutskever and G. E. Hinton Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 1097-1105, 2012.
6. M. H. Memon and J. Li and I. Memon and Q. A. Arain. GEO matching regions: multiple regions of interests using content based image retrieval based on relative locations *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 76,14,15377-15411, 2017.
7. Q. A. Arain and H. Memon and I. Memon and M. H. Memon and R. A. Shaikh and F. A. Mangi. Intelligent travel information platform based on location base services to predict user travel behavior from user- generated GPS traces *International Journal of Computers and Applications*, 39, 3, 155-168,2017.
8. M. H. Memon and J. Li and I. Memon and R. A. Shaikh and F. A. Mangi. Efficient object identification and multiple regions of interest using CBIR based on relative locations and matching regions *12th International Computer Conference on Wavelet Active Media Technology and Information Processing (ICCWAMTIP)*, 247-250,2015.
9. I. Memon and L. Chen and A. Majid and M. Lv and I. Hussain and G. Chen Travel recommendation using geo-tagged photos in social media for tourist *Wireless Personal Communications* Volume 80, Issue 4, pp 1347–1362, 2015.
10. M. H. Memon and I. Memon and J. Li and Q. A. Arain IMRBS: image matching for location determination through a region-based similarity technique for CBIR *International Journal of Computers and Applications*, 1-14, 2018.
11. T. Mäenpää and M. Pietikainen. Classification with color and texture: jointly or separately? *Pattern Recognition*, 37(8): 1629–1640, 2004.
12. V. Kumar and S. Minz. A survey on feature selection methods. *Smart Computing Review*, 4(3): 216–2229, 2014.
13. G. Chandrashekar and F. Sahi. A survey on feature selection methods *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 40: 16–28, 2014.
14. M. Pietikäinen, T. Ojala, and Z. Xu. Rotation-invariant texture classification using feature distributions. *Pattern Recognition*, 33(1):43 – 52, 2000.
15. L. Nanni, S. Brahmam, and A. Lumini. A simple method for improving local binary patterns by considering non-uniform patterns. *Pattern Recognition*, 45(10):3844–3852, 2012.
16. B. Yang and S. Chen. A comparative study on local binary pattern (LBP) based face recognition: Lbp histogram versus LBP image. *Neurocomputing*, 120:365–379, 2013. Image Feature Detection and Description.
17. G. NGirish, C.L. Shrinivasa Naika, and P. K. Das. Face recognition using mb-lbp and pca: A comparative study. In *2014 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics*, pages 1–6, Jan 2014.
18. V. Takala, T. Ahonen, and M. Pietik?inen. Block-based methods for image retrieval using local binary patterns. In *Image Analysis, SCIA*, volume LNCS, 3540, 2005.
19. T. Ojala, M. Pietikäinen, and T. Maenpaa. Multiresolution gray-scale and rotation invariant texture classification with local binary patterns. *Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, IEEE Transactions on*, 24(7):971–987, Jul 2002.
20. H. Zhou, R. Wang, and C. Wang. A novel extended local-binary-pattern operator for texture analysis. *Information Sciences*, 178(22):4314 – 4325, 2008.
21. D. T. Nguyen, S. R. Cho, and K. R. Park. Human age estimation based on multi-level local binary pattern and regression method. In *Future Information Technology*, page 433–438, 2014.

22. S. Bekhouche, A. Ouafi, A. Benlamoudi, A. Taleb-Ahmed, and A. Hadid. Automatic age estimation and gender classification in the wild. In *Proceeding of the International Conference on Automatic control, Telecommunications and Signals ICATS'15*, 2015.
23. W. Wang, W. Chen, and D. Xu. Pyramid-based multi-scale lbp features for face recognition. In *Multimedia and Signal Processing (CMSP), 2011 International Conference on*, volume 1, pages 151–155, May 2011.
24. SE. Bekhouche, A. Ouafi, F. Dornaika, A. Taleb-Ahmed, and A. Hadid. Pyramid multi-level features for facial demographic estimation. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 80(Supplement C):297 – 310, 2017.
25. F. Dornaika, A. Moujahid, Y. El Merabet, and Y. Ruichek. Building detection from orthophotos using a machine learning approach: An empirical study on image segmentation and descriptors. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 58:130 – 142, 2016.
26. A. Moujahid, F. Dornaika, . A pyramid multi-level face descriptor: application to kinship verification *Multimed Tools Appl*, (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-018-6517-0>.
27. S. H. Huang. Supervised feature selection: A tutorial. *Artificial Intelligence Research*, 4(2):22–37, 2015.
28. Z. Peng, P. Gurram, H. Kwon, and W. Yin. Sparse kernel learning-based feature selection for anomaly detection. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 51(3):1698–1716, 2015.
29. Y. Sun and D. Wu. Feature extraction through local learning. *Statistical Analysis and Data Mining*, 2(1):34–47, 2009.
30. Y. Sun, S. Todorovic, and S. Goodison. Local learning based feature selection for high dimensional data analysis. *IEEE Transactions ON Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 32(9):1–18, 2010.
31. X. Zhou and J.J. Wang. Feature selection for image classification based on a new ranking criterion. *Journal of Computer and Communications*, 3:74–79, 2015.
32. J. A. Sáez, J. Derrac, J. Luengo, and F. Herrera. Statistical computation of feature weighting schemes through data estimation for nearest neighbor classifiers. *Pattern Recognition*, pages 3941–3948, 2014.
33. J. Luengo, S. García, and F. Herrera. On the choice of the best imputation methods for missing values considering three groups of classification methods. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 32(1):77–108, Jul 2012.
34. S. H. Davarpanah, F. Khalid, L. Nurliyana Abdullah, and M. Golchin. A texture descriptor: Background local binary pattern (bglbp). *Multimedia Tools Appl.*, 75(11):6549–6568, June 2016.
35. F. Bianconi, R. Bello, P. Napoletano, and F. Di Maria. Improved opponent colour local binary patterns for colour texture classification. In *Workshop Computational Color Imaging Workshop, CCIW*, 2017.
36. C. Silva, T. Bouwmans, and C. Frélicot. An extended center-symmetric local binary pattern for background modeling and subtraction in videos. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Computer Vision Theory and Applications - Volume 1: VISAPP, (VISIGRAPP 2015)*, pages 395–402, 2015.
37. J. Kannala and E. Rahtu. Bsif: Binarized statistical image features. In *Pattern Recognition (ICPR), 2012 21st International Conference on*, pages 1363–1366, Nov 2012.
38. X. Tan and B. Triggs. Enhanced local texture feature sets for face recognition under difficult lighting conditions. *IEEE Trans. Image Processing*, 19:1635–1650, 2010.
39. T. Ahonen, A. Hadid, and M. Pietikinen. Face description with local binary patterns: application to face recognition. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 28(12):2037–2041, 2006.
40. T. Ahonen, E. Rahtu, V. Ojansivu, and J. Heikkilä. Recognition of blurred faces using local phase quantization. In *International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, pages 1–4, Dec 2008.
41. R. Lan, Y. Zhou, and Y. Y. Tang. Quaternionic local ranking binary pattern: A local descriptor of color images. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 25(2):566–579, Feb 2016.
42. N. Dalal and B. Triggs. Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2005. CVPR 2005. IEEE Computer Society Conference on*, volume 1, pages 886–893. IEEE, 2005.
43. O. Tuzel, F. Porikli, and P. Meer. A fast descriptor for detection and classification. In *European Conf. on Computer Vision*, pages 589–600, 2006.

44. P.N. Belhumeur, J.P. Hespanha, and D.J. Kriegman. Eigenfaces vs. fisherfaces: Recognition using class specific linear projection. In Bernard Buxton and Roberto Cipolla, editors, *Computer Vision — ECCV '96*, volume 1064 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 43–58. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1996.
45. F.S. Samaria and A.C. Harter. Parameterisation of a stochastic model for human face identification. In *Applications of Computer Vision, 1994., Proceedings of the Second IEEE Workshop on*, pages 138–142, 1994.
46. The Georgia Tech Face Database <ftp://ftp.ee.gatech.edu/pub/users/hayes/facedb/>
47. The FEI face database <http://fei.edu.br/cet/facedatabase.html>
48. Z. Fan, M. Ni, Q. Zhu, C. Sun, L. Kang, L0-norm sparse representation based on modified genetic algorithm for face recognition, In *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, Volume 28, Pages 15-20, 2015
49. L. Zhang, M. Yang and X. Feng, Sparse representation or collaborative representation: Which helps face recognition?, In *International Conference on Computer Vision*, Barcelona, 2011, pp. 471-478. doi: 10.1109/ICCV.2011.6126277
50. A. Beck and M. Teboulle A Fast Iterative Shrinkage-Thresholding Algorithm for Linear Inverse Problems In *SIAM Journal on Imaging Sciences*, 2009 2:1, 183-202
51. S. J. Kim, K. Koh, M. Lustig, S. Boyd and D. Gorinevsky, An Interior-Point Method for Large-Scale ell_1 -Regularized Least Squares, In *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 606-617, Dec. 2007. doi: 10.1109/JSTSP.2007.910971
52. Z. Liu, J. Pu, T. Huang and Y. Qiu (2013) A novel classification method for palmprint recognition based on reconstruction error and normalized distance. In *Applied Intelligence* 39:407–414
53. Q. Zhu, N. Yuan, D. Guan, N. Xu and H. Li An alternative to face image representation and classification. In *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13042-018-0802-0>
54. Donghai Guan, Weiwei Yuan, Young-Koo Lee, Kamran Najeebullah and Mostofa Kamal Rasel A Review of Ensemble Learning Based Feature Selection. In *IETE Technical Review*, 2014, 31, 3, 190-198.
55. Szeliski, Richard, Computer vision algorithms and applications. In *Computer Vision*, Springer, London; New York (2011), pages 812.
56. Jushan Bai and Shuzhong Shi Estimating High Dimensional Covariance Matrices and its Applications, In *ANNALS OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE* 12-2, 199-215 (2011)
57. Laloux, L., P. Cizeau, J. P. Bouchaud, and M. Potters. Noise Dressing of Financial Correlation Matrices. In *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1999, 83, 1467.
58. Laloux, L., P. Cizeau, J. P. Bouchaud, and M. Potters. Random matrix theory and financial correlations. In *International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Finance*, 2000, 3, 391-397.
59. Quanquan Gu, Zhenhui Li, and Jiawei Han. Generalized Fisher score for feature selection. In In Proceedings of the Twenty-Seventh Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence, 2011, (UAI'11), Fabio Cozman and Avi Pfeffer (Eds.). AUAI Press, Arlington, Virginia, United States, 266-273.
60. Daphne Koller and Mehran Sahami. 1996. Toward optimal feature selection. In In Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML'96), Lorenza Saitta (Ed.). Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA, 284-292.
61. Robnik-Sikonja, M. and Kononenko, I. Theoretical and Empirical Analysis of ReliefF and RReliefF In *Machine Learning* (2003) 53: 23.
62. Xiaofei He, Deng Cai, and Partha Niyogi. 2005. Laplacian score for feature selection. In In Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS'05), Y. Weiss, B. Schölkopf, and J. C. Platt (Eds.). MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, USA, 507-514.